

Notes on legal requirements

Supplement to “Requirements for Completion of the Ramp-up Phase”:
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Disclaimer: *This document is a guidance tool provided by Base4NFDI and does not constitute legally binding advice. It is tailored to the Ramp-Up phase of Research Data Management (RDM) services. Legal requirements may vary based on specific institutional policies and national implementations of EU Regulations. Service teams must consult their institutional legal and data protection offices for formal approval.*

1. Overview

This legal annex provides detailed guidance to support service teams in implementing the legal and data protection requirements described in **Deliverable D.RUp. 2**. It is designed to help teams:

- Understand their responsibilities in relation to intellectual property, licensing, data protection, accessibility, and terms of use.
- Guide them in documenting their compliance clearly and consistently.
- Discuss measures to meet legal obligations at the Ramp-Up Phase and beyond.

This annex does not introduce new legal requirements. Service teams remain responsible for consulting institutional legal, data protection, or accessibility offices where needed. Base4NFDI aims to provide guidance, coordination, and template support upon explicit request.

2. Scope and Applicability

The legal requirements described in this document follow the principle of applicability. Service teams should evaluate which sections are relevant based on their specific technical setup, data types, and user base.

What service teams should evaluate:

- **Assess Relevance:** Determine which legal areas (Intellectual Property, GDPR, etc.) apply to the current state of the service.
- **Document Scoping Decisions:** If a requirement is deemed "not applicable" (e.g., no personal data is processed), briefly document the reasoning.
- **Re-evaluate Periodically:** Revisit this annex if the service evolves or adds new features.

3. Intellectual Property and Licensing

What this means in practice

Service teams must identify and document ownership of all results created, including software code, documentation, workflows, configurations, datasets, and other service-related outputs. Ownership must be clearly defined, even when development involves multiple institutions.

To support the FAIR principles, teams should distinguish between licenses used for software (for example, MIT or Apache 2.0) and licenses applied to data or metadata. Metadata should ideally be licensed under CC0 or CC-BY to ensure maximum

discoverability and reuse. Further practical recommendations on licensing choices and service design considerations are provided in the *Base4NFDI Service Design Guide*.¹

Third-party components, libraries, services, or datasets are subject to their own licenses. Teams must ensure that these licenses allow intended use, integration, and distribution. Obligations may include attribution, inclusion of license texts, or restrictions on redistribution. Where services process or store user-generated content, ownership, licensing conditions, and responsibility for such content must be clearly described.

What service teams should consider

- Identify all components and outputs that form part of the operational service.
- Document who owns the results created by your service team, such as software code, documentation, workflows, or datasets. This usually means identifying the responsible institution or project that developed these components and providing clarity regarding ownership.
- Select and document appropriate licenses for service outputs, using machine-readable formats (e.g., SPDX identifiers or URI links).
- List all third-party components (e.g., via a Software Bill of Materials/SBOM) and confirm license compatibility.
- Fulfill attribution or citation requirements where required.
- Clearly describe ownership and licensing conditions for user-generated content.

4. GDPR and Data Protection

What this means in practice

Processing of personal or sensitive data requires a clear purpose and a valid legal basis (e.g., consent, legitimate interest). Only data necessary for service operation should be collected (data minimisation).

Teams must define their legal role under the GDPR: is the institution a Sole Controller, Joint Controller, or Data Processor? This determines which legal templates (e.g., Art. 26 or Art. 28 GDPR) are required.

Transparency is essential: teams must be able to explain what data is collected, processed, stored, and accessed, and for how long. Some services may require a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) if processing poses higher risks. Services should implement Privacy by Design, documenting how technical measures (e.g., pseudonymisation or automated deletion) are enforced.

¹ Base4NFDI Service Design Guide, section 4.5.2.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16306726>

What service teams should consider

- Identify all personal and sensitive data processed and define the legal role (Controller/Processor).
- Document the purpose and legal basis for each data category.
- Maintain a Record of Processing Activities (ROPA) where required.
- Describe data flows at a high level, including collection, processing, storage, and international transfers.
- Clarify access rights, storage locations, and authentication methods.
- Reference applicable privacy notices and institutional policies.
- Document retention, deletion, backup, and archiving practices.
- Designate a post-Ramp-Up contact and provide a short description of the data incident response plan.

5. Accessibility and Inclusive Access

What this means in practice

Accessibility is both a legal requirement and a core principle for publicly funded digital services in Germany. Services should therefore be usable by people with diverse abilities and should follow applicable accessibility standards. For further guidance on the legal and technical aspects relevant to service development, please refer to our [Guidelines on Application of Web Accessibility](#).²

At the Ramp-Up stage, full accessibility may not always be achieved. Transparency is required: known limitations must be documented, and improvement plans should be outlined. Publishing an Accessibility Statement on the service website is essential and must include a feedback mechanism to allow users to report barriers.

What service teams should consider

- Identify applicable accessibility requirements
- Document implemented accessibility measures and record known limitations.
- Outline planned improvements and a timeline for remediation.
- Publish and reference an Accessibility Statement with a clear contact point for user feedback.
- Include results of accessibility testing, audits, or user feedback where available.

² <https://zenodo.org/records/15719660>

6. Terms of Use and User Obligations

What this means in practice

Services that are accessible to users must clearly define the conditions under which they may be used. This typically includes rules for acceptable behaviour, responsibilities related to uploaded or created content, and limitations of liability.

For research data management services in particular, the terms of use should also explain how the service will handle user content that may infringe copyright or violate applicable law. This usually involves a notice and take-down procedure, which describes how problematic content can be reported and how the service will review and remove such content when necessary.

For many research infrastructure services, terms of use operate on two different levels.

1. First, there are terms that apply to the direct users of the service. These describe how researchers or other users may access and use the service. They usually include acceptable use rules, responsibilities related to user-generated content, and any limitations of liability.
2. Second, the service may be operated within infrastructure provided by an institution or within a shared technical environment. In these cases, institutional policies, hosting platform rules, or other infrastructure-related terms may also apply.

Service teams should therefore clarify which rules apply at each level and how they relate to one another. It is acceptable to rely on existing institutional terms of use, but it should always be clear where these terms can be accessed. Service teams should also verify which institutional rules apply to their service and, where necessary, consult their institutional legal or policy offices to ensure compliance.

What service teams should consider

- Document the terms of use that apply specifically to the researchers or users of the service.
- Clarify obligations when uploading data, creating content, or interacting with the service.
- State explicitly where institutional or infrastructure-level terms (e.g., hosting platform rules) also apply.
- Provide direct links to all relevant documents and maintain a version history (e.g., "Last Updated" date) to track changes from Ramp-Up to full operation.
- Briefly explain how service-specific rules interact with institutional or hosting terms to avoid legal gaps.

- Confirm alignment with institutional policies and, where relevant, German consumer and contract law.

7. Roles, Responsibilities, and Support

- **Service Teams:** Responsible for documenting compliance within their institutional context and consulting local data protection officers or legal support teams of your institutions.
- **Support from Base4NFDI:** Aims to provide guidance, template drafts, and reviews of draft documentation. Base4NFDI also facilitates the exchange of **best practices** between different service teams to harmonise compliance across the network.
- **Limitation:** This support facilitates consistent compliance but does not replace formal legal advice provided by the home institution.

8. Conclusion

This annex provides guidance on the key legal areas relevant to services during the Ramp-Up Phase and supports service teams in understanding the expectations related to legal compliance. Service teams remain responsible for implementing these requirements and ensuring transparency in areas such as ownership of results, licensing, data processing, accessibility, and the terms under which the service may be used.

Where questions arise regarding legal interpretation or institutional policies, teams are encouraged to consult their institutional legal or data protection offices. In addition, Base4NFDI can provide guidance to support services in understanding and documenting the legal topics described in this annex and may assist in clarifying compliance approaches where appropriate.